

DISTENDER Project Monitoring Report I

D10.2: Monitoring report summarizing the progress of the scenario development and test cases, and the implementation of the DSS I

WP10, T10.2: Evaluation of the level of achievement of the project objectives

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1 Preface

This report describes methodology and results of the first project monitoring cycle for the EU Horizon project DISTENDER.

The overall DISTENDER project objective is to co-design integrated strategies by building a methodological framework that guides the integration of climate change (CC) adaptation and mitigation strategies through participatory approaches in ways that respond to the impacts and risks of present and future socio-economic and climate trends. This is supported by quantitative and qualitative analysis that facilitates the understanding of interactions, synergies and trade-offs. From the project's start, a specific project monitoring framework was planned and implemented in order to link the highly specialized and technical work done in the context of the individual work packages to the achievement of the overarching project objectives, and to maximize middle and long terms impacts of DISTENDER.

The monitoring concept and the monitoring itself are part of Work Package 10 – Project Monitoring. The purpose of the Work Package is to support the members of the project consortium - consisting mainly of researchers, case study representatives, and external stakeholders from the case studies - in efficiently structuring their work and becoming clear about, assessing, and optimizing the long-term impacts of their work beyond the context of DISTENDER.

Drawing on the theoretical monitoring framework developed in deliverable D10.1, this report outlines the development of measurement tools and the implementation and results of the first project monitoring period. The report presents the information on the review of the methodology, results of the first monitoring period and a discussion on collected feedbacks and learnings.

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2 Methodology

This chapter presents the methodologies used to collect data on the current status of the DISTENDER project. It aims to provide valuable project monitoring information. To this extent, it outlines the process of developing and selecting tools, explains the creation of the monitoring schedule, and describes the implementation and rollout of the developed tools.

2.1 Tool development and selection

The selection of tools for monitoring DISTENDER followed the framework established in D10.1, chapter 3.3. The toolbox employed consists of four different methods of data collection: (i) surveys, (ii) interviews, (iii) direct and (iv) indirect observations.

Initially, all the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and 115 outcomes defined in D10.1 were assessed in terms of their optimal implementation in a closely coordinated co-creation approach by ADELPHI research and LINKS.¹

Most of the outcomes that can be quantitatively measured (such as those on a Likert scale) were transformed into survey questions (using a 5-point scale). Also, outcomes related to a larger audience, such as all DISTENDER case studies, were transformed in survey questions. As a result, we obtained a set of 88 survey questions for the first monitoring cycle. In some cases, transforming the KPIs into questions required small adjustments with respect to the KPI itself. The resulting questionnaire applied two question types, standard questions (e.g. O.3, *“How satisfied are you with the quality of workshops conducted?”*) and statements (e.g. O.10, *“To which degree do you agree with the following statement: ‘I have a sense of ownership regarding the results of the Distender project.’”*). These questions were answered on a Likert scale from 1 to 5, with 1 consistently representing the low/negative end of the scale, or strong disagreement, and 5 representing the high/positive end of the scale, or full agreement. Open questions were used for outcomes requiring background knowledge not available to the WP10 team (e.g. O.15, *“Please list platforms used by WP11 for citizen engagement.”*). Moreover, certain open-ended questions were incorporated to assess the participants' comprehension of specific concepts by prompting them to provide definitions. This approach aimed to evaluate the potential acquisition of knowledge throughout the project. (e.g. O.47, *“Please briefly define the concepts of “climate adaptation” and “climate mitigation” and describe the difference between the two, stating examples.”*).

Outcomes requiring some organizational overview were included in templates for indirect observations to be completed by Work Package leaders. That applied also to outcomes that required monitoring over extended periods of time (e.g. the frequency of conducted workshops). The observation templates included also questions with only one possible answer, like the total number of conducted workshops. The Work Package leaders act as intermediaries collecting information and play a vital role in supporting project monitoring. They gather and summarize information that they have access to by virtue of their positions within DISTENDER. In total, five of these observation templates were created and distributed (for WPs 2, 3, 4, 6 and 9). Outcomes related to events (e.g. workshops or panels) have also been assessed through direct observations by WP10 members to further increase the robustness of data available to the monitoring team.

¹ For an explanation of the term “outcome” refer to D10.1, p. 14.

Finally, interviews were chosen for outcomes that required additional context information to be collected from the participants. These interviews were conducted via online calls in a semi-structured format.

2.2 Monitoring schedule

In D10.1, we assigned for each outcome a measurement interval. In most cases, outcomes will be measured either biannually or annually, with some outcomes to be measured at the end of the project or at specified times. This approach is in line with the concept of formative monitoring for DISTENDER as it results in continuous monitoring of the project KPIs (see D10.1, chapter 2.1). Thus, we provide the project partners with relevant information on the project's progress and ways to improve it.

A measurement schedule was set up to determine which outcomes are to be assessed at specific points during the project. In accordance with the current version of the DISTENDER Work Plan, some questions were excluded from the first monitoring cycle since the addressees had not yet started working on the relevant subjects. Future changes to the Work Plan may result in subsequent changes to the monitoring schedule, for example when modelling rounds are completed later than initially foreseen and related outcomes can only be assessed after the modelling has finished. To best capture relevant information for each envisaged outcome, the monitoring team needs to closely track organizational changes to the project and adapt the data collection approach when necessary.

The first monitoring cycle was conducted in March 2023 (project month 10) and served a number of objectives:

- To provide a baseline measurement for future result comparisons;
- To test the developed tools in terms of usability (both for WP10 and the participants);
- To raise awareness among the DISTENDER partners for the monitoring process and the KPIs they need to report on;
- To gather feedback on the measurement process that can be used to enhance future monitoring endeavors.

2.3 Implementation

2.3.1 Online survey

To ensure the widest possible distribution of the DISTENDER monitoring survey and create a strong database for the impact analysis, we set up an online questionnaire using the online survey tool LimeSurvey. This approach enabled the development of a user-friendly and practical online survey, which could be conveniently distributed among DISTENDER partners and case study participants across Europe. The survey is securely hosted on an adelphi research server, thus minimising implementation efforts and costs and providing additional data protection, as no data is stored or processed by third parties.

All of the data collected via the survey was anonymous, and no personal information beyond the addressees' gender and role in the project was obtained. To guarantee the participant's data privacy, the survey was evaluated and approved by ADELPHI research's data protection officer².

² Sema Karakas, Althammer & Kill GmbH & Co. KG, Thielenplatz 3, 30159 Hannover, Germany

When participants followed the survey URL (see chapter 2.3.3), they were directed to a landing page summarizing the project’s monitoring objectives and the survey’s format (Figure 1).

DISTENDER Project Monitoring (WP10)

Dear DISTENDER partners,

thank you for your interest in participating in the project monitoring for DISTENDER.

as WP10, we are tasked with monitoring the development and progress of DISTENDER throughout the project. The aim of our project monitoring plan is to maximize the impact of DISTENDER by monitoring what aspects of the project work are successful (with respect to achieving impact), and in which areas changes might be necessary to ensure that we achieve the highest impact possible.

To collect the data, **we require your help and cooperation** – only a sufficient number of participants and an appropriate quality of information will allow us to accurately monitor the project, which in turn will benefit everybody involved in DISTENDER.

The following questionnaire will contain questions that are tailored to your specific role in DISTENDER. As part of the monitoring process, you will be asked to answer some of these questions repeatedly over the course of the project.

Please answer all of the questions to your best knowledge. If a question is unclear or you cannot answer it, please still answer the remaining questions and give us feedback at distender@adelphi.de.

Thank you for your participation!

WP10

Next

Figure 1: Screenshot of the online survey landing page (as shown during first measurement period)

Once participants clicked the “Next” button on the landing page, they were prompted to create a *self-generated identification code*. This is an established method to maintain the participant’s anonymity while creating a unique signifier specific to the participant for each data entry. In this way we ensure that the monitoring of KPI changes over the project’s duration can be optimized by matching answers from the same participants collected in multiple survey rounds (Schnell et al. 2010; Yurek et al. 2008). The self-generated identification code was implemented by having participants complete the same code generation form in each survey round. This form utilized information that is familiar to the participant but not known to the researcher, allowing them to generate a unique string of characters. This code can then be used for data matching purposes at a later stage. However, this method poses challenges such as false-negative cases (i.e. participants do not replicate the same code at different times, so their answers cannot be matched) and false-positive cases (i.e. multiple participants enter the same code, and their answers are erroneously matched) (Schnell et al. 2010). To avoid false-negative cases, the personal information the code is to be generated from was chosen to be as stable as possible, so that participants are likely to give the same answer, and thus generate the same code, at each survey iteration. In order to avoid false-positive cases, the code was chosen to contain 10 digits from five questions:

1. The last 2 letters of the participant's father's first name (e.g. AdAM)
2. The first 2 digits of the participant's birthday in DD/MM/YYYY format (e.g. 01 for 01 February, 1999)
3. The last 2 letters of the participant's place of birth (e.g. BarceloNA)
4. The checksum of the participant's year of birth (e.g. 1999: 1+9+9+9 = 28; with leading zeroes for single-digit numbers, e.g. 2000: 2+0+0+0 = 02)
5. The first 2 letters of the participant's mother's first name (e.g. EVe)

The resulting code for this example would be "AM01NA28EV". Assuming a 26-letter alphabet and 28 days/month for question 2, the code formula allows for

$$26^2 \times 28 \times 26^2 \times 10^2 \times 26^2 = 864,964,172,800$$

permutations, clearly exceeding the potential number of participants and significantly reducing the chance of two participants generating the exact same code, even when non-random variable distributions are considered (e.g. the range of potential names for questions 1, 3 and 5 in reality does not extend over all letters of the alphabet in random order). The code entry field was coded to only accept codes with the correct format (10 digits: 2 letters, 2 numbers, 2 letters, 2 numbers, 2 letters), and the rest of the survey was only accessible after creating a valid identification code.

While Schnell et al. (2010) point out that higher matching success for data series can be achieved by creating even longer code chains, the 10-digit format was deemed to provide a sufficient balance of false-positive prevention while simultaneously being easy enough to navigate as to not hinder participants from answering the survey. Yurek et al. (2008) report smaller numbers of errors and omissions for question set characteristics that focus on the participant rather than others, but it was chosen to ask for name characteristics of the participant's parents instead of their own name, since this might have posed a small risk of participants being identifiable to the WP10 members.

After successfully creating their identification code, participants were asked to provide some general information about themselves, namely their gender and their role within DISTENDER. Depending on participants' stated role, additional questions were displayed to further detail their answer. For example, selecting the answer "*I am part of a Work Package*" was followed by a list of all Work Packages to choose from. Similarly, participants affiliated with the DISTENDER (follower) case studies were asked to specify which case study they were associated with.

From a technical standpoint, LimeSurvey's logical branching feature was employed to implement these variations in survey questions based on participants' previous answers. This functionality allowed for assigning conditions to each question, so that a question would only appear if a particular response was provided in a previous question. Since the vast majority of outcomes is connected to specific groups of experts within DISTENDER, the tool was used for all questions in the survey. Each question was only visible to the pre-determined group of recipients, resulting in individual surveys with a variable number of questions based on the addressee group.

After responding to the final question related to their selected project role, participants were presented with a concluding message thanking them for their time and participation.

2.3.2 Indirect Observation templates

As mentioned for specific outcomes we selected the method of indirect observations as appropriate. After formulating the questions referring to these outcomes, these questions were grouped according to the intended addressees, resulting in six sets. For each addressed WP an individual PDF form containing the relevant observations and explanations on when and how to record the data was created. These forms also contained instructions on the frequency at which the data should be reported back to WP10.

2.3.3 Roll-out of monitoring tools

The monitoring process was laid out to the DISTENDER partners through a number of e-mails, as well as announcements during Steering Committee and General Meetings. Additionally, some Work Packages were contacted individually in case of a particular need for participation. The online survey was shared with all DISTENDER partners, and further dissemination among the Work Packages, stakeholders and (follower) case studies was encouraged.

Observation templates were shared with the respective Work Package leaders, along with a detailed explanation of the information to be collected. Finally, interviews were scheduled with the respective Work Package leaders, and sharing of future workshops and events was encouraged in order to allow for direct observations to be carried out by the members of Work Package 10 in future monitoring cycles.

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3 Results of first monitoring period

The following chapter unveils the findings from the initial monitoring cycle. Since the questions in the survey varied depending on the participant's project role, it's important to note that the sample size is relatively small (refer to chapter 3.1). A substantial share of the questions were answered by only a limited number of recipients. For this reason, we did not apply advanced statistical analysis of the results in this monitoring cycle. In general, results are shown as a bar graph for easier understanding. Each graph is labelled with the question text, as used in the survey. In cases with little additional insight gained through a bar graph, tables are used to display the results. Where only one sole response was provided or qualitative answers were given, the question is quoted and the results are described instead of visualized.

Only fully completed surveys are included in the survey analysis. Please note that the number of answers per question (n) can vary, since it was possible to skip most questions.

3.1 Participation

In total, the data collection produced 65 survey entries (32 incomplete, 33 complete), four filled-in observation templates and two interviews with Work Packages participants.

3.1.1 Online survey

Out of 32 incomplete survey entries, 24 stopped filling in the survey before creating the self-generated identification code, implying that the process of code generation can be an obstacle for participants. However, only eight participants went through the code generation process and did not finish the survey, with the majority providing no more than a few answers before exiting the survey. Against this background, it is possible that the code generation step is merely a filter for those participants who do not have the time or intention to complete the survey at that point of time.

In total, we collected 33 completed survey entries from 25 individual participants, identifiable by their identification codes. Some participants filled in the survey multiple times to account for their multiple roles in the project. Among the 25 participants, a slight majority identified as male (14 male, 11 female, see **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**).

The vast majority of survey participants (26) were affiliated with one or more Work Packages, with only four participants affiliated with a (follower) case study (see Figure 2). The three participants who selected the "other" option used the free-text field to indicate they were affiliated with follower case studies. However, by not selecting the "(Follower) Case Studies" option, they were not presented with any additional questions specifically tailored

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to their role. To avoid this problem in future surveys, an explanatory prompt will be added to ensure selection of the correct option.

Figure 2: What is your role in DISTENDER?

The fact that external stakeholders and policymakers did not participate in the survey on can be attributed to the DISTENDER Work Plan: Stakeholder activation had not yet or only just begun at the time of the first monitoring cycle. This was confirmed by Work Packages 2 and 9, who stated that stakeholders were not yet involved with DISTENDER and could not be included at this stage. As a result, a considerable number of questions did not receive any responses and, therefore, will not be included in this monitoring report. However, the existing question set for external stakeholders and policymakers will be used during the next monitoring cycles, the results of which will then constitute the external stakeholder and policymaker data baseline.

Additionally, the survey will be modified. Clarification will be provided for policymakers. Policy makers are mostly involved through the case studies. The current distinction might be confusing and lead to policymakers not knowing which option to choose – which also might be a cause for the absence of any policymaker in the first monitoring cycle. In future survey rounds, the question for the policymaker status will be added as a separate question presented to participants choosing the “case study” answer.

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Figure 3: Which Work Package are you affiliated with?

Among the participants from Work Packages, participation was relatively homogenous, with all WPs contributing two to four answer sets. After coordinating with WP10, WP2 decided to fill in the survey as a group, in line with the co-creation approach established for the project and reflecting the mode of operation in WP2.

Figure 4: Which (follower) case study are you affiliated with? (F = follower case study)

As mentioned, participation from Case Studies and Follower Case Studies was low in the first monitoring cycle: answers were collected from three out of five case studies and one out of six follower case studies (see Figure 4). However, as stated earlier, some Follower Case Studies participants were excluded due to incorrect utilisation of the questionnaire.

Throughout the measurement process, WP9 reached out to the (Follower) Case Studies repeatedly to increase participation, but for future measurements, a more sustained effort to gather survey participants from this group might be necessary.

3.1.2 Indirect observations

During the first monitoring cycle, four out of the five distributed observation templates (WPs 2, 3, 4 and 9) were utilized by Work Packages to provide information to WP10. In two instances, recipients raised some questions regarding the indirect observations, which were subsequently addressed by WP 10 during interviews. This made it possible to collect the observed data. The missing data from WP6 can be attributed to the DISTENDER Work Plan, with WP6 starting to operate only shortly before the monitoring cycle.

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3.2 Results by impact dimensions

In D10.1, ten impact dimensions were distinguished to monitor the impact of DISTENDER (see D10.1, chapter 2.4); outcomes were categorized along nine of these dimensions. In this chapter, results are presented according to the impact dimensions. The number of the according outcome is noted next to the corresponding survey or observation template question (e.g. O.3). Unless noted otherwise, results were collected from the online survey.

3.2.1 Co-creation

In the observation template, WP9 was asked about the number of meetings they expect and plan to have with the case study participants and stakeholders (O.2). Up to the first monitoring cycle, WP9 had organized five official meetings, with two of them specifically addressing the interaction between modellers and case study partners. For May-June 2023, five scenario workshops are planned for the core case studies, some of them online and some of them on location of the case study. Future meeting schedules will depend on the demand and specific needs of the individual case studies and stakeholders.

Figure 5: How satisfied are you with the quality of workshops conducted in DISTENDER? (O.3)

During the first monitoring cycle, satisfaction with workshops (O.3) was surveyed among the Work Packages that had organized workshops up to that point, and among case study participants. As shown in Figure 5, overall, workshop satisfaction was largely neutral, but trended towards satisfaction. Notably, positive answers were provided by participants from case studies.

Another observation template question to WP9 concerned the types of stakeholders and entities WP9 plans to include in the case study workshops and meetings (O.6). The answer pointed to participants from public and private authorities, SMEs, higher education and research, independent experts, associations/NGOs, financial service providers and members of the general public.

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Figure 6: How likely are you to use the method of co-creation in the context of other policy fields (e.g. urban planning) in the future? (O.4)

Case study participants were also asked how likely they were to use the co-creation method utilized in DISTENDER in the context of other policy fields in the future. The feedback was very positive, with half of the answers indicating a very likely application of the approach in future policy work (Figure 6).

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3.2.2 Participation

Case studies participants and stakeholders were surveyed about their level of involvement and the impact of climate change on them (e.g. to what degree do you feel personally affected). As depicted in Figure 7, participants from the (follower) case studies for the most part feel moderately to strongly involved in climate change challenges. The only dissenting voice comes from the Austria case study, indicating a slight level of involvement.

The same addressees were also asked about their degree of identification with the results of DISTENDER. Here, the most frequent answer was “undecided”, with a single vote towards identification with the results of the project (Figure 8).

Figure 7: How would you describe your level of involvement and perceived stake in climate change challenges? (O.9)

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Figure 8: I can identify with the results of DISTENDER as a whole. (O.10)

Another question to stakeholders and case study participants was aimed at the individual level of contribution to their DISTENDER workstream (Figure 9). Most answers stated an average contribution, with one participant describing their contribution as high. The outlier (no contribution) can be explained by the participant’s affiliation with a follower case study, where work had not yet begun under the DISTENDER Work Plan at the time of monitoring.

Figure 9: How would you describe your level of individual contribution to the specific results of the workstream you are involved in? (O.11)

Participants of WP11 were presented with a series of questions on citizen engagement. First, they were asked to state their view on engagement platforms’ diversity. Survey

participants were mostly undecided, but leaned towards sufficient diversity (Figure 10). Additionally, we asked if alternative channels were utilised sufficiently to engage difficult-to-reach demographics (one answer – “undecided”). Participants from WP11 were asked to specify platforms used for citizen engagement in a free-text field, which was answered with “project website” and “LinkedIn”.

Figure 10: The diversity of engagement platforms used is sufficient. (O.15)

Another question to WP11 revolved around whether DISTENDER provides concrete ideas and options for citizen engagement and participation. The answers trend towards mild agreement (Table 1).

Table 1: The DISTENDER project provides concrete ideas and options for citizen engagement and participation. (O.16)

Answer option	1 strongly disagree	2 disagree	3 undecided	4 agree	5 strongly agree
number of answers	0	0	1	1	0

Finally, WP11 members were asked to indicate their satisfaction with the achieved level of outreach at this point, which proved to be moderately high (Figure 11).

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Figure 11: Are you satisfied with the achieved level of outreach regarding the communication, dissemination, and exploitation KPIs? (O.17)

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3.2.3 Network

Figure 12: Connections have been made between stakeholders on exchanging experiences and best practices from other pilot studies. (O.19)

As shown in Figure 12, case study participants did moderately agree regarding connections that had been established between stakeholders, with one participant disagreeing. However, it is important to note that the absence of answers from stakeholders and the early stage of stakeholder activation at the time of monitoring imply that the results of this question may not be representative at this point.

Figure 13: The DSS provides the potential for long-term interdisciplinary cooperation. (O.21)

All Work Package members were asked about their perspective on the Decision Support System (DSS) developed in DISTENDER. Participants were nearly unanimously in agreement that the DSS provides the potential for long-term interdisciplinary cooperation (Figure 13).

Figure 14: I am willing to keep up the established networking structures after the project ends. (O.22)

A similarly positive picture is shown in Figure 14, with 22 out of 28 participants agreeing that they would be willing to keep up the networking structures established in DISTENDER for other projects. This question was aimed at all survey participants, regardless of their specific role in the project. However, it is noteworthy to consider the single disagreeing vote from a Work Package member, showing that the need for or satisfaction with the established structures varies within the project.

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3.2.4 Science-policy and science-science interaction

Figure 15: To what extent are uncertainties addressed in your WP work (e.g. methodological improvements in form of better qualification of potential uncertainties)? (O.25)

The participants of the Work Packages were questioned about the extent to which uncertainties were addressed in their work. The results indicate average to moderate consideration of uncertainties (Figure 15).

Figure 16: How would you rate your own knowledge of scientific methods (e.g., using data, modelling processes, etc.)? (O.27)

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Additional feedback on this question was provided in the official WP10 meeting on April 6, 2023, where clarification on the types of uncertainties was requested in order to provide correct answers. The request will be addressed in future survey iterations by adding an explanatory prompt; for now, the recorded results must be viewed with some reservations, as participants answered the question based on their individual interpretation of uncertainties.

Case study participants and stakeholders were asked to assess their own knowledge of scientific methods, such as data processing and modelling (O.27) (Figure 16). The three received answers from case study participants indicate a fairly good understanding of scientific methods.

As a follow-up question, the same addressees were surveyed on their improvement in understanding of scientific methods in research projects (like data management and decision-making) since the beginning of the project (Table 2). While the provided answers encompass the full range of answer options, it is important to evaluate this question in conjunction with O.27: the participant stating “no improvement” had already a fair understanding of scientific methods before the start of the project, while the participant answering “strong improvement” has a good understanding of scientific methods due to the participation in DISTENDER.

Table 2: How would you rate the extent of improvement in your understanding of scientific methods in research projects (e.g., data, processes, and decision-making) since the beginning of the project? (O.28)

Answer option	1 no improvement	2 little improvement	3 some improvement	4 moderate improvement	5 strong improvement
number of answers	1	0	1	0	1

Another set of questions assessed the awareness of project partners’ needs for scientific inputs. As Figure 17 shows, Work Package members’ answers regarding improvements in their understanding of stakeholders’ needs cover most of the scale’s range, from “no improvement” (one answer) to “moderate improvement” (six answers). 16 out of 17 answers indicate some degree of improvement, and the “moderate improvement” option (4 out of 5 on the Likert scale) accounts for more than a third of the provided answers. A more detailed analysis reveals that highest improvements were recorded by members of WP9, who worked in close contact with case studies and external stakeholders, whereas lower improvement was mostly indicated by members of the more method-focussed Work Packages (WPs 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8).

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Figure 17: To what extent have you acquired through DISTENDER a better understanding of stakeholder needs regarding scientific input (e.g. stakeholder needs at different government levels)? (O.29)

Case study participants were inquired about their perception of the extent to which DISTENDER scientists comprehended the issues presented to them. Two-thirds of the participants agreed that DISTENDER scientists possess a good understanding of the problems raised by the case studies (Figure 18).

Figure 18: The scientists have adequately grasped the problems presented by the case studies. (O.30)

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Policymakers and members of WP6 were asked: *“To what extent do you agree with the following statement: The scientific solutions developed from risk assessments support existing policies and strategies, e.g. the EU Green Deal”* (O.31). The sole recorded answer was from a member of WP6: “3 – neutral”. More meaningful data might be obtained when policymakers actively participate during the next monitoring cycle.

Table 3: How much progress have you made (how much has your understanding improved) regarding pertinent input data to climate models run? (O.32)

Answer option	1 no progress	2 little progress	3 some progress	4 moderate progress	5 strong progress
number of answers	0	1	1	1	1

Participants of WP4 were surveyed on the progress that was made regarding the pertinent input data for climate model runs. As shown in Table 3, all answers imply some level of progress, but the assessment of magnitude varies from “little progress” to “strong progress”. However, it should be noted that these answers are relative to pre-existing knowledge of the participants, so “little progress” could be associated with a very high level of understanding that was not significantly improved upon in DISTENDER.

Case study participants, stakeholders and policymakers were asked whether they were able to learn from downscaling techniques and the co-design of climate indicators applied in DISTENDER (Table 4). The participant from a follower case study who strongly disagreed, who was not able to benefit from the DISTENDER methodology as he was not actively integrated into the project workflow. The other answer, provided by a participant in a case study, indicates moderate learning success.

Table 4: I have been able to learn from downscaling techniques and the co-design of climate indicators applied in DISTENDER. (O.34)

Answer option	1 strongly disagree	2 disagree	3 neutral	4 agree	5 strongly agree
number of answers	1	0	0	1	0

Participants of WP5 were inquired on whether they could successfully work with climate model outputs in the DISTENDER impact models (Table 5). The first responses were positive.

Table 5: In the DISTENDER impact models, I am able (have been able) to work with climate model outputs successfully. (O.35)

Answer option	1 strongly disagree	2 disagree	3 neutral	4 agree	5 strongly agree
number of answers	0	0	0	1	1

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Participants of WP6 were asked, “How would you rate the understanding policymakers have of the goals of the DISTENDER project?” (O.36), with the sole answer stating “1 – no understanding”. While the sample size is too small to draw robust conclusions, this indicates that the understanding policymakers have of the project goals has to be closely monitored in order to avoid a loss of potential impact. Obviously, the answer could also reflect the limited interaction between WP6 and policymakers at this point in the project.

Table 6: Scientific output is delivered and communicated in accessible language. (O.42)

Answer option	1 strongly disagree	2 disagree	3 neutral	4 agree	5 strongly agree
number of answers	0	0	0	1	1

Case study participants, stakeholders and policymakers were asked about the presentation of scientific output in DISTENDER (Table 6 and Table 7). The answers provided by case study participants indicate that scientific output is communicated in accessible language and with comprehensible reasoning.

Table 7: Scientific output is delivered and communicated in a logical way (with comprehensible reasoning). (O.42)

Answer option	1 strongly disagree	2 disagree	3 neutral	4 agree	5 strongly agree
number of answers	0	0	0	1	1

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Figure 19: The outputs of my work have been adequately translated into the DSS. (O.44)

The Work Packages with modelling tasks (WPs 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7) were asked whether their outputs were adequately translated into the DSS (Figure 19). Two participants agreed that this was the case, 5 out of 8 answers were neutral, one participant from WP6 strongly disagreed. This is especially interesting because at the time of the first monitoring, DSS design had just started according to the Work Plan. That might explain the many answers with neutral. Regarding the disagreeing answer the implied problem had probably already occurred during the DSS user requirement collection. As part of the project monitoring, WP6 and WP8 will be informed to provide the opportunity to address this issue.

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3.2.5 Awareness and understanding of climate change issues

Case study participants, stakeholders and policymakers were asked whether key concepts emerging from the project were adequately formulated and adopted (Table 8), with the overall feedback being positive.

Table 8: Key concepts which emerged from the project were adequately formulated and adopted. (O.46)

Answer option	1 strongly disagree	2 disagree	3 neutral	4 agree	5 strongly agree
number of answers	0	0	1	1	1

The same addressee groups were asked to provide short explanations of the two concepts of climate change adaptation and climate change mitigation, to assess their base knowledge and potential improvements in future measurement rounds. While a grading scale for these answers is yet to be developed by WP10, all case study participants showed a good grasp of both concepts and the difference between them.

Case study participants, stakeholders and policymakers were also asked about their understanding of uncertainties associated with scientific model outputs (Figure 20). The results indicate that two participants have a moderate understanding of scientific model output uncertainties, while one participant claims to possess a high level of knowledge in this area.

Figure 20: I have a good understanding of the potential uncertainties of scientific model outputs and their characteristics, e.g. internal/external uncertainties. (O.50)

Uncertainties were also the topic of a question for the participants of WPs 3, 4 and 5. They were asked if uncertainties were sufficiently and appropriately considered in the modelling

process. The responses exhibit some variability, but a majority of participants indicated a moderate level of consideration of uncertainties in the modelling process (Figure 21).

Figure 21: Are uncertainties considered sufficiently and in an appropriate way in the modelling? (O.51)

A rather diverse range of answers was provided for a question, in which case study participants, stakeholders and policymakers were asked whether they had gained knowledge on climate change financing through DISTENDER (Table 9). While the strongest negative answer once again was provided by a follower case study participant that had little opportunity to learn in the context of the project so far, it is notable that one of the case study participants also denied substantial learning effects. However, this can also indicate that substantial knowledge in this sector already existed before DISTENDER and does not allow for drawing conclusions about the actual level of background knowledge that exists among the case study participants. Also, further insight in climate change financing might yet be acquired during the course of the project.

Table 9: My knowledge of climate change financing (e.g. EU taxonomy) has increased through participation in the DISTENDER project. (O.57)

Answer option	1 strongly disagree	2 disagree	3 neutral	4 agree	5 strongly agree
number of answers	1	1	0	1	0

Next, participants of the modelling Work Packages (WPs 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7), case study participants and policymakers were questioned on their level of satisfaction with the visualisations of climate change issues provided in DISTENDER, with answers ranging from neutral to strong agreement and a weighted average of 4 out of 5. The answers indicate moderate satisfaction (Figure 22).

The participants of modelling Work Packages were asked about their familiarity with downscaling methods for climate modelling. As shown in Figure 23, answers trend towards higher familiarity, but range from slight to strong familiarity. More detailed analysis shows that the highest scores were reported by WPs 3, 4 and 5, with average scores reported by WP6, and WP7 providing more diverse answers ranging from “slightly familiar” to “moderately familiar”.

WP11 participants were asked, “How many third-party researchers (of other EU research projects and networks) have been directly involved through DISTENDER?” (O.64). One participant from WP11 answered, with the given estimate being “2”.

Figure 22: The visualisations of complex climate change issues provided in DISTENDER are accurate and useful. (O.58)

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Figure 23: How familiar are you with downscaling methods for climate modelling? (O.63)

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3.2.6 Implementation

Participants of Work Packages 4 and 5 were asked how they rated the availability and usability of local level data for modelling purposes. The answers range from “poor” to “very good” availability, with a tendency towards “good” (weighted average: 3,71) (Figure 24).

Figure 24: How do you rate the availability and usability of local level data for modelling purposes? (O.67)

In the observation template, WP4 was asked about the number of individual local/regional climate simulations that were or are expected to be built by combining downscaled Earth System Models under different socioeconomic scenarios (O.68). In total, WP4 statistically downscaled 60 simulations, of which a representative set of $3 \times 6 = 18$ simulations were selected for each CCS. Additionally, six simulations are planned for each DISTENDER round, using dynamical downscaling of the most representative CMIP6 model. The six planned simulations are: (1) Reference simulation (2) Historical Simulation, (3) SSP126, (4) SSP245, (5) SSP370, and (6) SSP585.

Another observation template question for WP4 concerned different downscaling techniques (O.69). WP4 plans to employ mostly two types of downscaling: statistical downscaling techniques (SDTs) and dynamical downscaling techniques (DDTs).

In the observation template, WP4 was also asked to provide the smallest area currently covered by downscaled simulations (O.70). At the time of the first monitoring cycle, the smallest resolution was achieved for Guimarães (Portugal), at 100m. The regional domain used for dynamical downscaling has a horizontal resolution of approx. 3.9km.

In an open survey question, participants of WP4 were asked, “How do you estimate the costs of downscaling processes (computing, energy, staff, etc.) necessary for the application of the DSS in individual contexts?” (O.71). The answers state that costs would be very high, but made the distinction that SDTs would be much cheaper than DDTs. One answer provided specific numbers, estimating that SDTs would cost 24,000€ per CCS while DDTs would cost 240,000€ per CCS, a tenfold increase in costs.

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Case study participants and policymakers were queried on whether the developed indicators adequately addressed the challenges and vulnerabilities identified by the stakeholders. The responding case study participants expressed agreement with this notion (Table 10).

Table 10: The developed indicators adequately cover the challenges and vulnerabilities identified by the stakeholders. (O.72)

Answer option	1 strongly disagree	2 disagree	3 neutral	4 agree	5 strongly agree
number of answers	0	0	0	2	0

Participants of WP5 were queried how confident they were that created indicators are applicable across different scales. The answers range from disagreement to agreement (Table 11).

Table 11: I feel confident that the created indicators are applicable across different scales. (O.75)

Answer option	1 strongly disagree	2 disagree	3 neutral	4 agree	5 strongly agree
number of answers	0	1	1	1	0

Follow-up case study participants were asked, *“To what extent are you able to design own robust strategies based on the DISTENDER findings?”* (O.80). The sole received answer was “1 – not at all”, but once again it remains unclear if this is due to the fact that follow-up case studies are not yet active in DISTENDER, or if the answer is supposed to convey criticism of the project. The same answer was also given for the question, *“To what extent are you able to replicate strategies or individual measures that were applied in pilot cases?”* (O.81).

Participants of WP11 were asked, *“Based on the feedback you received, how do you rate the probability that third parties will be interested and willing to use DSS within their own specific contexts? If possible, please provide examples”* (O.84). One answer was given (“3 – undecided”), with an accompanying comment that pointed out it was too early in the project to state this.

3.2.7 Cost-efficiency

No questions associated with this impact dimension were asked in the first monitoring cycle.

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3.2.8 Integration of adaptation and mitigation

Case study participants were surveyed about their level of understanding regarding the advantages and disadvantages of integrating climate change adaptation and mitigation in the project. According to Table 12 15, all participants indicated a “somewhat informed” status. In the comment field, one participant stated that the information did not originate from DISTENDER, but from other projects. Another participant pointed out that for them, the concepts cannot be separated in their field of work. And one participant stated expertise on peatland management as an example on how both concepts work together in an integrated way.

Table 12: How well do you feel informed on advantages and disadvantages of integrating climate change adaptation and mitigation? (O.94)

Answer option	1 not informed at all	2 very little informed	3 somewhat informed	4 moderately informed	5 very well informed
number of answers	0	0	3	0	0

Participants of WP4 were asked to provide their perspective on the sensitivity of the model output quality to the type of input data. They agreed that the quality of the model outputs is very sensitive to the input data (Table 13). In the attached commentary field, it was clarified that the output quality of the model is sensitive to the quality of the input, but the quality of the model itself is not influenced by this. Additionally, it was noted that SDTs are much less sensitive to this influence than DDTs.

Table 13: How sensitive is the model output quality to the type of adaptation/mitigation input data? (O.95)

Answer option	1 not sensitive at all	2 slightly sensitive	3 moderately sensitive	4 very sensitive	5 extremely sensitive
number of answers	0	0	0	2	0

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3.2.9 Cross-sector and multi-scale

Participants of WP3 were asked how applicable and adaptable the developed socio-economic scenarios are across different scales and sectors (Table 14). The answers indicate good to very good applicability of the scenarios for different scales and sectors.

Table 14: How well are the developed socioeconomic scenarios applicable/adaptable across different scales and sectors? (O.102)

Answer option	1 not at all	2 little	3 somewhat	4 well	5 very well
number of answers	0	0	0	1	1

WP4 was surveyed on the usefulness of global climate scenarios for initiating a downscaling chain to local scenarios. The results show that all participants strongly agree with the proposed statement, implying high significance of global climate scenarios for the creation of local scenarios (Table 15).

Table 15: Global climate scenarios are useful in initiating a downscaling chain to local scenarios. (O.105)

Answer option	1 strongly disagree	2 disagree	3 neutral	4 agree	5 strongly agree
number of answers	0	0	0	0	4

Case study participants, external stakeholders and policymakers were asked, “How would you rate the extent to which indicators defined in WP5 were useful in sectors beyond those predefined in the Grant Agreement?” (O.106). One case study participant answered, stating that the indicators were “very useful” (value 4 on a 5-point scale).

WP5 participants were queried about the effectiveness of the developed risk assessment in addressing different scales. The answers imply medium to moderate capability. (Note: for part of the measurement period, this question was mistakenly displayed to a wider range of addressee groups than intended. The error was subsequently rectified, and answers from unexpected addressee groups were excluded.)

Table 16: To what extent is the developed risk assessment capable of addressing different scales? (O.107)

Answer option	1 not capable at all	2 slightly capable	3 somewhat capable	4 moderately capable	5 very capable
number of answers	0	0	1	1	0

WP5 participants were inquired about, “Which topics/sectors (e.g. health, environment, policy) are covered by the climate scenarios?” (O.108). In the comments, it was pointed out that the question should ask for climate impact assessments rather than climate scenarios. While this will be corrected in the next survey iteration, two other WP5 participants provided answers as originally intended. They identified that health, water, energy, socio-economic topics and environment, as well as Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use (AFOLU) are encompassed .

Finally, case study participants, stakeholders and policymakers were asked to what extent adaptation and mitigation are being integrated into non-climate strategies in their study area, and to provide examples of such strategies. One participant from the case study in the North-East of the Netherlands stated that both concepts are completely absent from non-climate strategies. Conversely, a participant from the case study in Dehesas (Spain) and Montados (Portugal) answered that adaptation and mitigation are partially integrated into non-climate strategies, citing forest management as an example.

Table 17: To what extent are adaptation and mitigation integrated into non-climate strategies? (O.111)

Answer option	1 not at all	2 little	3 somewhat	4 moderately	5 very much
number of answers	1	0	1	0	0

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4 Discussion

Overall, the results of the first DISTENDER project monitoring cycle show that the monitoring plan initially drafted in D10.1 is a suitable framework for project monitoring. The developed KPIs and outcomes could be adequately transformed into monitoring tools, and informative data was collected.

Upon reviewing the provided data, it can be observed that the majority of KPIs currently indicate average/neutral to positive states. Some critical assessments provided relevant contextual information or highlighted areas for improvement to be considered in future monitoring cycles. However, with no responses from external stakeholders and only modest participation from the participants of (follower) case studies, the significance of the project monitoring will have to be underlined and participation encouraged in future rounds.

4.1 Feedback, identified shortcomings and learnings

The first monitoring cycle highlighted a number of issues with the chosen methodology that need to be addressed in future iterations of the project monitoring.

The feedback received through various channels (e-mail, interviews, meetings) indicated a common concern: Although a significant portion of questions had already been excluded for the first monitoring cycle, the monitoring still contained a substantial number of questions that could not be answered by the participants due to the stage of the project. To some degree, this situation was anticipated, and participants were informed that they could provide estimations of expected results in cases where they concrete data was not yet available. This would have allowed for creating a baseline measurement while also providing insights into the expectations for the project among the participants. However, many participants felt uncertain about providing even educated guesses for some of the answers, further reducing the available database for analysis in the first monitoring cycle round. Assuming normal progress of the project, this problem will likely diminish over the course of the project runtime, without requiring additional actions from WP10.

In the next online survey iteration, it is important to better account for the partners with multiple roles in DISTENDER. This can be achieved by allowing participants to select multiple roles at the beginning of the survey, displaying all questions related to all selected roles. This approach would reduce confusion among the participants, and eliminate the need to restart the survey for each role. Clear and consistent communication about this new approach could also enhance participation and ensure a better data set. However, it will also increase the perceived workload of the participants due to longer surveys, potentially leading to a higher rate of unfinished surveys.

During the interview with WP9, it was pointed out that when addressing local stakeholders from the case study areas, there is a risk that they may have limited English language skills making it difficult for them to answer specific questions in the online survey. To address this, there are several potential strategies. One option is having the affiliated Work Package leaders pre-select stakeholders with sufficient English language proficiency. However, this approach may reduce the representativeness of the data as it would only include stakeholders with good English skills, chosen by the Work Package leaders, which could also increase their workload. Another option is to simplify the language used in the questions

This option poses a risk of misrepresenting the original outcome when adapting the questions, potentially losing a crucial level of accuracy. The third option is to translate the questionnaire into appropriate languages. But, this would involve additional costs and needs to be carefully evaluated from a project management perspective.

During interviews, it was occasionally pointed out that some outcomes were not directed towards the appropriate addressee, and that other DISTENDER participants were better equipped to provide certain information. This feedback was documented and will be used to enhance the accuracy of data collection in future monitoring cycles.

Finally, a number of minor technical improvements were implemented in the survey during the first monitoring cycle based on direct feedback from participants, such as the option to move backwards through the survey and view questions already answered. Further adjustments and modifications are possible at any given time during the monitoring process and will be made where necessary.

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5 Conclusions

This report presents the creation, development and roll-out of the first DISTENDER project monitoring cycle. In the following, the key results are briefly summarized:

- The DISTENDER project monitoring framework, initially outlined in D10.1, was successfully transformed into an operational monitoring process.
- The developed tools functioned as intended and proved suitable for data collection in the context of the project monitoring.
- Participation in the project monitoring was generally satisfactory. However, the limited presence or low engagement of certain addressee groups reduced the amount of collected data and possible conclusions drawn. In future iterations, it is crucial to ensure higher participation from all DISTENDER partners to achieve project monitoring and include diverse perspectives.
- The timing of the first monitoring round in the DISTENDER Work Plan played a role in reduced participation numbers, with some addressees of questions not yet involved in the project.
- During the monitoring process, useful feedback was provided by many DISTENDER partners, which will be used to optimize and streamline the monitoring process for future monitoring cycles.
- The data overall shows moderate to positive trends for nearly all KPIs for which meaningful data could be collected. In cases where feedback was more ambivalent, plausible explanations were generally identified.
- Greater participation and more diverse participants in terms of their role within DISTENDER are necessary for more robust data analysis in the future.

The results of this report will be disseminated among the project consortium and all relevant groups and individuals in the project. This dissemination aims to provide them with insights into the state of the project, stimulate reflection on the work done so far, and facilitate the adaptation of new or improved strategies to maximise the impact achieved in DISTENDER.

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References

Schnell, Rainer; Bachteler, Tobias; Reiher, Jörg (2010): Improving the use of self-generated identification codes. In: *Evaluation review* 34 (5), S. 391–418. DOI: 10.1177/0193841X10387576.

Yurek, Leo A.; Vasey, Joseph; Sullivan Havens, Donna (2008): The use of self-generated identification codes in longitudinal research. In: *Evaluation review* 32 (5), S. 435–452. DOI: 10.1177/0193841X08316676.

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